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Halide and Oxidehalide Complexes of Chromium with 2,2'-Bipyridine

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CHROMYL chloride may act as a Lewis acid and form addition compounds with donor molecules. Some examples are known^{1,2}, but other possibilities have not been fully explored, nor the compounds well studied. No complex bromides or iodides have been reported. Complex compounds of chromium in oxidations states other than 2 and 3

are not many³, particularly the oxidehalide complexes in 4, 5 and 6 oxidation states are rare and of low stability.

The present communication gives a preliminary report on some 2,2'-bipyridine complexes of chromium in 6, 4, 3 and 1 oxidation states.

Experimental

Chromyl chloride was prepared by the usual method and 2,2'-bipyridine was of reagent quality. Acetic acid and benzene were purified and dried as usual.

Compounds prepared with their elemental analysis and some physical and chemical properties are given in table 1.

Magnetic moment measurements were made at room temperature (28°C) by the guoy method and the corrected values of the magnetic moments were 1.08, 3.28 and 3.35 for (I), (II) and (IV) respectively which is taken to indicate the presence of 0, 2 and 3 unpaired electrons in the *d*-levels of chromium³.

Conductivity measurements at room temperature in purified formamide solutions at different concentrations did not give a straightline plot (Λ vs \sqrt{c}) and Λ_0 value was found to be 58 ohm⁻¹ cm², showing that the compound is a weak electrolyte.

The infra-red spectra of the compounds have been recorded in Nujol mull from 4000 cm⁻¹ to 700 cm⁻¹. None of these compounds exhibit any i.r. peak beyond 2900 cm⁻¹ and hence O-H group is absent. The strong bipyridine peak at 763 cm⁻¹ has shifted to 775 cm⁻¹ and a weak one at 730 cm⁻¹ to 735 cm⁻¹ with increase in intensity on complexation. (I) shows two peaks at 955 cm⁻¹ and 895 cm⁻¹ which are due to Cr-O. A common peak at 980 cm⁻¹ is present in (II) and (III) and they are assigned to Cr-O. (IV) does not contain any peak between 1000 cm⁻¹ and 800 cm⁻¹ which proves the absence of Cr-O group in conformity with chemical evidence.

TABLE I

Compounds	Mode of preparation	Analytical results	General properties
(I) Dioxodichloro-2,2'-bipyridine chromium (VI) CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	By the interaction of chromyl chloride and bipyridine in acetic acid medium in the cold.	Found : Cr = 16.44%; Cl = 21.40; N = 8.84, Valency = 6.0. Calculated : Cr = 16.70, Cl = 22.80, N = 9.0, valency = 6.0.	Red, Stable, Solid, slowly decompose on storage. Sensitive to light, moisture and heat. Insoluble in water.
(II) Mono-oxo-di-iodo-2,2'-bipyridine chromium (IV) CrOI ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Reducing (I) with hydroiodic acid solution.	Found : Cr = 10.70, Cl = 52.10, valency = 4.1. Calc.: Cr = 10.87, I = 53.13, valency = 4.0.	Deep violet stable solid, rather inert. Sparingly soluble in water and other common organic solvents.
(III) Mono-oxo-monochloro-2,2'-bipyridine chromium (III) CrOCl.C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Isothermal heating of (I) for 4 hours at 200°-280°C in N ₂ -atmosphere.	Found : Cr = 19.77, Cl = 13.80, loss = 15.67. Calc.: Cr = 20.00, Cl = 13.70, loss = 16.56.	Greenish, stable solid.
(IV) Chloro (2,2'-bipyridine) chromium (I) CrCl.C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ *	Isothermal heating in dry N ₂ -atmosphere at 370° to constant weight.	Found : Cr = 21.99, Cl = 15.77, valency = 0.95. Calc.: Cr = 21.40, Cl = 14.57, valency = 1.0.	Black solid, insoluble in water and most other common solvents. Rather inert.

* When (IV) is prepared most of the chlorine is evolved as HCl and bipyridine in (IV) appears to be partly oxidised.

Studies in similar lines are in progress.

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Isolation of Some Sterol Glucosides and a Triterpene from *Mollugo Hirta*

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THE isolation of new triterpenoid sapogenins from *M. hirta* was reported earlier¹⁻⁴. The present paper reports the isolation of a mixture of two sterolglucosides and oleanolic acid from the same source.

The ethanolic extract of the air-dried powdered plant was concentrated and the glycosides were precipitated with ether and hydrolysed with acid in the usual way (*loc. cit.*) for 20 min. The aglycones were taken up in chloroform and separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Chloroform: ethanol (90:10) eluate furnished a crystalline compound, m.p. 272°-76°(d) which showed a single spot in t.l.c. over silica gel G as well as silica gel G impregnated with aqueous AgNO₃ solution (12.5%). It gave violet → green colour in the Liebermann Burchard test indicating it to be a sterol. Moreover, its mass spectrum showed peaks at m/e 574 (C₃₅H₅₈O₆) and 576 (C₃₅H₆₀O₆) besides two other

peaks at m/e 412 (C₂₉H₄₈O) and 414 (C₂₉H₅₀O) which could be explained as due to the loss of glucosyl moiety (C₆H₁₁O₅) from the molecular ions with transfer of one H-atom as shown here:

and this suggested the compound to be a mixture of two sterol glucosides.

The above mixture of sterol glucosides furnished on acid hydrolysis, glucose (identified by paper chromatography) and a mixture of two sterols which showed two spots in t.l.c. over silica gel G impregnated with silver nitrate solution and the spots corresponded to those of β -sitosterol and γ -sitosterol respectively. The above mixture was acetylated and column chromatography of the product furnished β -sitosterol acetate and γ -sitosterol acetate, identified by comparisons of m.p. mixed m.p. and I.R. spectra with authentic samples. So the glucoside isolated by us is a mixture of the glucosides of β -sitosterol and γ -sitosterol.

The acid sapogenin fraction was esterified with diazomethane and chromatographed over silica gel. Benzene: chloroform (2:1) eluate furnished a compound m.p. 198°-99°, which formed an acetate, m.p. 220°-21°. These were identified as methyl oleanolate and acetyl methyl oleanolate respectively by comparison of m.p., mixed m.p. and I.R. spectra with the authentic samples.

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